

MEDICAL SCIENCES

COMPLEX TREATMENT OF INFLAMMATORY DISEASES IN PERIAPICAL TISSUES

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Abstract

With the growing amount of information about methods and means aimed at treating destructive forms of apical periodontitis, it has become necessary to conduct a review of the available literature that would form a general understanding of the existing treatment methods and highlight modern approaches to solving this issue. This review describes the techniques of conservative treatment of apical periodontitis, their advantages, and disadvantages. The relevance of the problem motivates scientists from different countries to develop innovative materials that contribute to the restoration of destructive processes in bone tissue, as well as methods that reduce the trauma and risks of invasive treatment.

Keywords: apical periodontitis, conservative treatment of periodontitis, periodontitis physiotherapy, calcium hydroxide, synthetic osteoplastic materials, calcium hydroxyapatite, apical therapy.

Chronic Apical Periodontitis (Destructive Osteitis) is a focus of chronic intoxication and sensitization of the body, posing a potential threat of developing acute or chronic osteomyelitis of the jaws. The treatment of chronic destructive osteitis is one of the significant challenges faced by a dentist in practical work. Conservative treatment aims to eliminate microbial flora, stimulate regenerative processes in the bone of the periapical area, and ensure complete obturation to prevent reinfection of the root canal system and periodontal tissues. It is also the least traumatic method for the patient.

The issue of instrumental and pharmacological influence on destructive processes in the apical region has been widely debated for many years and continues to be discussed. The traditional technique of sanitizing the apical focus through the root canal is not always effective. Currently, methods of active drainage through the root canal, trepanation hole, and root apex are proposed for sanitizing the pathological focus. The active non-surgical decompression technique involves using the Endo-ze vacuum system, which, by creating negative pressure, leads to the decompression of large periapical lesions. The suction aspirator is connected to a micro-needle, which is inserted into the root canal and activated for 20 minutes, creating negative pressure.

Exudate aspiration occurs during the procedure. When the outflow partially stops, the access cavity is sealed with temporary cement to prevent microorganism penetration. Unlike the decompression technique, this method is minimally invasive, and the entire procedure is performed through the root canal, causing less discomfort to the patient.

Decompression Technique:

The decompression method involves placing a drain at the apex of the root in the focus of the lesion.

Regular irrigation of the focus must be carried out, along with periodic adjustments of the drain's length and replacement over various time periods. The drain can be a modified cannula, a fragment of rubber dam, a polyethylene tube with a stent, a hollow tube, a polyvinyl tube, a drainage catheter, or a radiopaque latex tube. There are no standard requirements for the duration of drainage placement, as the drain comes in various sizes and lengths depending on the localization and extent of the lesion. The drain may remain in place for a period ranging from two days to five years. The patient is required to irrigate the focus of the lesion daily through the drain lumen using 0.12% chlorhexidine. This is a simple procedure that minimizes the risk of damaging adjacent vital structures and is well-tolerated by the patient.

However, there is a possibility of developing inflammatory reactions of the oral mucosa adjacent to the drainage tube, displacement and obstruction of the drainage tube, and the development of acute or chronic infections.

Deposition of copper-calcium hydroxide:

Besides its bactericidal effect, it helps to block the lumen of hard-to-pass root canals and enhances osteoblast activity in the periapical tissues. In intracanal electrophoresis, dissociated drug ions, such as potassium iodide, antibiotics, and enzymes (trypsin), penetrate more effectively into body tissues.

Ultrasonic waves in a liquid medium create steam bubbles (cavitation effect) and vortex flows around the endodontic tip, which helps to break down detritus in the root canal and heat the antiseptic solution. In addition to the aforementioned methods of physiotherapy for apical periodontitis, high-frequency electric fields (UHF), fluctuating currents, microwave therapy, and

darsonvalization are widely used. However, it is important to note that physiotherapy has its strict indications and contraindications for use. Thus, physical factors are applied during pharmacological and instrumental treatment, to alleviate inflammatory reactions before and after canal obturation, as well as to relieve post-obturation pain.

Temporary Root Canal Filling Technique:

According to modern concepts of treating apical periodontitis, the tooth cavity is left open only in cases of pronounced purulent exudation. In other cases, the root canals should be filled with materials that have antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory properties and stimulate regenerative processes in the periodontal tissues. Medications can remain in the root canals for several days to several months. For temporary filling, substances based on strong antiseptics (iodoform, thymol, camphor, menthol, paraformaldehyde, para-chlorophenol, etc.), antibiotics, corticosteroids, metronidazole, and calcium hydroxide are used. The caries research department of Niigata University has developed a concept based on the use of a triple paste containing ciprofloxacin, metronidazole, and minocycline. It is known that metronidazole has a broad antibacterial spectrum against anaerobes. It has been proven that the combination of these drugs, under the influence of ultrasonic waves, effectively penetrates through the dentinal tubules into the lumen of the root canal. Although the volume of medication used for this type of treatment is small, it is necessary to determine the sensitivity of the root canal microbiota to the effects of antibiotics. One disadvantage of the triple antibiotic paste is the discoloration of teeth induced by minocycline.

Mechanism of Action of Calcium Hydroxide:

When introduced into the root canal, the mechanism of action of calcium hydroxide is as follows:

1. The highly alkaline environment (pH about 12.4) provides a bactericidal effect, halts bone resorption, and promotes lysis of necrotized tissues.
2. Calcium ions participate in bone formation and blood coagulation.
3. Upon contact with moisture in the canal, the material expands in volume by 2.5 times, sealing macro- and microcanals and thereby ensuring their isolation.

Calcium hydroxide was first introduced by Hermann in 1930 as a pulp-capping material. Since then, clinical studies have been conducted, some of which confirm, while others contradict, the effectiveness of the material in treating destructive forms of periodontitis. According to Michalchenko D.V. (2014), the use of the "Calasept" product showed a 82.1% reduction in the size of the destructive focus after 6 months, and complete restoration of bone structure in 64.3% of cases after 12 months. Zoto F. (2015) described a 90% success rate of treatment with calcium hydroxide combined with 20% propolis oil solution and iodoform. However, difficulties arise in removing calcium hydroxide residues from the root canal. Nandini et al. (2006) reported that calcium hydroxide paste in an oil base is harder to remove from the canal than when it is mixed with distilled water. It is therefore recommended to remove the paste with calcium hydroxide using ultrasonic systems.

Additionally, Orucoglu (2008) reported that bone tissue regeneration occurs around the paste, but in some cases, the paste does not fully resorb.

The addition of barium sulfate to calcium hydroxide paste as a radiopaque substance complicates the resorption of the paste beyond the apex. However, Souza (2013) described complete resorption of calcium hydroxide paste within 15 days. Some studies have shown that prolonged exposure to calcium hydroxide in the root dentin can lead to brittleness and increased fragility of the tooth.

Use of Synthetic Osteoplastic Materials (Biomaterials):

Currently, there is an active search for materials capable of directly influencing the site of bone tissue destruction. New-generation drugs with many advantages include synthetic osteoplastic materials based on calcium hydroxyapatite. To improve the properties of these materials, calcium phosphate, β -tricalcium phosphate, collagen, antimicrobial agents, platelet-rich fibrin, growth factors, and nickel-titanium are added. It is known that synthetic hydroxyapatite activates endogenous growth factors and remineralizes atrophied bone.

V.N. Lenyev (2016) demonstrated that the use of osteoplastic materials is a highly effective method for treating destructive forms of periodontitis. Although hydroxyapatite is synthesized under high temperatures and does not exist in nature, it causes a biologically active reaction similar to natural processes occurring in bone tissue. Osteoblasts attach to hydroxyapatite, absorb it, and initiate the mechanism of cell proliferation and differentiation. Differentiating osteoblasts produce type I collagen, alkaline phosphatase, proteoglycans, and matrix proteins such as osteocalcin, osteonectin, and bone sialoproteins, which are known markers of bone formation.

Some of the main properties of synthetic materials include biocompatibility, bioactivity, biodegradability, porosity, osteoconductivity, and osteoinductivity. Additionally, the porous surface enhances the mechanical interaction (interpenetration) between the biomaterial and the surrounding newly formed bone, providing greater mechanical stability. Osteoconductivity refers to the ability to serve as a scaffold directing the formation and ingrowth of new bone along the material surfaces. Osteoinductivity refers to the material's ability to induce the differentiation of mesenchymal cells from surrounding non-bone tissues into chondrocytes, osteoblasts, and other bone-forming cells, typically demonstrated by bone formation following the implantation of biomaterials in ectopic sites.

For the treatment of destructive forms of periodontitis, synthetic osteoplastic materials are increasingly used. Among these are "Hydroxyapatite Gel," "CollapAn," "Trapex-Gel," "Hydroxyapol," "Indost," and "Ostim-100." In cystectomy treatments, the bone defect was filled with calcium hydroxyapatite. In 78.9% of patients from the main group, there was complete restoration of bone tissue in the area of destruction, with complications occurring in 5% of patients, which is 2.8 times less than in the comparison group, where a blood clot was used to fill the bone defect.

E.S. Khudyakova (2009) conducted apical therapy using bone-plastic materials. Restoration of the peri-apical bone tissue was $97.7 \pm 1.6\%$ after one year, and $99.3 \pm 0.6\%$ after three years. In his studies, R.M. Gizatullin (2009) used nanostructured hydroxyapatite gel (HANG) and porous nickel-titanium. The author demonstrated the success of the treatment. Interestingly, porous nickel-titanium integrates into newly formed bone tissue, acting as a scaffold. A.P. Sorokin (2014) described the effectiveness of treating destructive forms of periodontitis, with a success rate of 92.5% using "Bioimplant" and "CollapAn-gel" containing collagen, hydroxyapatite, and sulfated glycosaminoglycans.

V.V. Tairov et al. (2011) showed reliable results in the effectiveness of the "CollapAn-gel K" preparation ("Intermedapatit"), which can be improved by using ultrasonic treatment of the root canals. Gusiyska A. (2015) demonstrated positive dynamics in the treatment of destructive forms of chronic periodontitis using calcium hydroxyapatite and two-phase calcium phosphate.

However, Castro A.G.B. et al. (2017) showed that most calcium-phosphate materials have weak mechanical strength and slow resorption in body tissues. Therefore, despite the numerous positive characteristics, there is still a need for further improvement and elimination of the shortcomings of biomaterials.

The practical experience and knowledge accumulated by clinicians and researchers show that methods and means of conservative treatment for apical periodontitis have their advantages and disadvantages. The choice of methods and materials may be limited by indications and contraindications, depending on the clinical situation. However, innovative materials continue to be developed and tested, contributing to the restoration of destructive processes in bone tissue and reducing the trauma and risks of invasive treatment.

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